

Simultaneous Measurements of Temporal and Spatial Phase Structure Functions of an HF Skywave Signal at Mid-Latitudes

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of data collected with an HF/VHF interferometer in southern Maryland of skywave propagating signals from WWV near Ft. Collins, Colorado and CHU near Ottawa, Ontario. Using a four-antenna array with spacings of $\sim 100\text{--}350$ m near Pomonkey, Maryland, a four-hour test data collection was made of the 10 MHz signal from WWV in Feb. 2020. Measurements of the temporal and spatial phase structure functions (SFs) from this collection were used to constrain the coherence time and length as well as the relationship between the two. The temporal SFs indicated coherence times of $\sim 1\text{--}4$ s. By scaling the temporal SFs to match the spatial ones, it was found that the ratio of coherence length (on the ground) to coherence time was about ~ 200 m s^{-1} until near sunset when this ratio became highly variable and was $\sim 400\text{--}800$ m s^{-1} . A 30-day campaign in Oct. 2022 that used two of the four antennas to collect data from the 7.85 MHz skywave of CHU yielded similar results. These showed the coherence ratio systematically increasing from ~ 150 m s^{-1} at 17 UT (noon local time) to ~ 250 m s^{-1} at 22 UT (17 local time).

1 INTRODUCTION

The first over-the-horizon (OTH) wireless radio frequency (RF) systems used “skywave” propagation. Within the medium frequency (MF; 0.3–3 MHz) and high frequency (HF; 3–30 MHz) regimes, refraction due to RF interactions with free electrons within the ionosphere is extreme enough to produce total internal reflection back to the surface with the incoming signal appearing to come from the sky (hence the name). This has been used for decades by amateur radio operators and amplitude modulated (AM) radio stations for long-distance broadcasts. Even as satellite-based systems have become extremely prevalent in modern times, the cost benefits of ground-based skywave systems have ensured that they remain widely in use for communications and radar-based surveillance.

Skywave systems, however, are not without their drawbacks. The very medium they rely upon, the ionosphere, is not static but is populated with disturbances and irregularities on a wide variety of spacial scales. Irregularities on km scales in particular distort signal paths, impacting signal coherence. For OTH radars (OTHRs), for example, decreased temporal coherence leads to a broadened Doppler response, which can cause clutter returns to overlap with objects of interest, making them difficult to detect (i.e., the so-called “spread Doppler clutter” issue; see, e.g., Headrick and Thomason, 1998). Decreased spatial coherence likewise limits the angular resolution of any array-based HF system by broadening the beam.

The temporal and spatial coherence of a skywave signal can be characterized via measurements of the phase structure function (SF), the variance in the difference in phase between two points as

Figure 1: Upper: Time series of the WWV 10 MHz carrier frequency Doppler shift measured from the mean spectrum over all four DLITE antennas in (black) RHCP and (red) LHCP. Lower: The measured time of arrival (TOA) after the nearest UT second of each 5-ms pulse.

a function of their separation in either time or space. This is a key statistic used to characterize the impulse response of HF systems within propagation simulators (Nickisch, 1992; Nickisch et al., 2012). This paper presents an analysis of temporal and spatial SFs measured with a four-element interferometer near Pomonkey, Maryland using the skywave propagating 10 MHz signal from the WWV radio station near Ft. Collins, Colorado and the 7.85 MHz broadcast from CHU near Ottawa, Ontario. Sec. 2 details the observations and results with discussion and conclusions in Sec. 3.

2 OBSERVATIONS AND ANALYSIS

2.1 WWV

Observations of the WWV 10 MHz carrier wave were made with the Deployable Low-band Ionosphere and Transient Experiment (DLITE) near Pomonkey, Maryland on 14 Feb. 2020. As described in detail by Helmboldt et al. (2021), DLITE is an interferometer of four inverted vee dual linear polarization dipole antennas with baselines between ~ 100 – 350 m. These are normally used to monitor a handful of exceptionally bright cosmic radio sources at 35 MHz for the effects of km-scale ionospheric irregularities, which manifest as intensity scintillations. In this case, a special mode was implemented that allowed each antenna to record raw voltages at 10 MHz with 2.5 kHz of bandwidth. The linear polarizations were combined to form right and left hand circular (RHCP and LHCP, respectively) polarization voltages. Additional processing generated Doppler spectra of the carrier wave and also timed the 5-ms pulse emitted at the beginning of each UT second using a GPS-synched clock as a reference.

Time series of the Doppler shift and pulse time of arrival (TOA) are plotted in Fig. 1. One can see that at around 23.3 UT, the TOAs dropped and became somewhat more stable, indicating a transition from two-hop to one-hop propagation. One can also see that significant Doppler disturbances

occurred just after 24 UT, shortly before the channel disappeared. To measure temporal SFs free from the influence of non-repeating portions of the signal, i.e., the time code (modulated at 100 Hz), the voice announcements (modulated at 500 or 600 Hz), and the on-the-second pulses (modulated at 1 kHz), the voltages were averaged down to a bandwidth of 100 Hz. Then, for each antenna and polarization and within each minute of data, the mean cross correlated amplitude of the signal times another portion of the signal from Δt seconds later, $X(\tau, \Delta t) = |\langle V(t)V^*(t + \Delta t) \rangle|$, was computed with Δt stepped in 0.1 s increments where V is the complex voltage and τ is the time at the middle of the one-minute segment. In each case, the mean auto-correlation amplitude of each of the signals, $A(\tau) = \Re[\langle V(t)V^*(t) \rangle]$, was also computed such that the correlation coefficient could be calculated, i.e., $R(\tau, \Delta t) = X(\tau, \Delta t)/\sqrt{A(\tau)A(\tau + \Delta t)}$. It was then assumed that the phase SF was $= -2 \ln[R(\tau, \Delta t)]$. The coherence time (i.e., the value of Δt where SF = 1) from these SFs was about 1–2 s for the time period of two-hop propagation (UT < 23.3) and about 2–4 s for the one-hop time period (23.3 < UT < 24.2), i.e., about twice as long as the two-hop case.

The spatial structure function was similarly computed, but using the full 2.5 kHz bandwidth. In this case, the correlation coefficient was computed within one-minute intervals by multiplying the voltages from each of the six unique baselines in the array with no temporal delay applied. The resulting spatial SFs averaged within five-minute bins are plotted as circular points in the upper panels of Fig. 2 with RHCP and LHCP in black and red, respectively. Within each of these intervals, the mean temporal SFs were also computed per antenna and polarization. For each antenna/polarization, the ratio of the coherence length, r_{coh} , to the coherence time, t_{coh} , that was needed to bring the spatial and temporal SFs into agreement was iteratively determined. The resulting scaled temporal SFs are also plotted in the upper panels as curves, and one can see that this simple scaling method generally results in good agreement between the two types of SFs.

The lower panel of Fig. 2 shows the time series of the coherence ratio, r_{coh}/t_{coh} , averaged over all four antennas. Prior to the appearance of significant Doppler disturbances after 24 UT, this ratio is quite stable at $\sim 200 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and similar for both one- and two-hop propagation. Within this time period, there is some evidence of a sinusoidal pattern oscillating about a mean of 205 m s^{-1} with a period of 43 minutes and amplitude of 29 m s^{-1} . After 24 UT, the ratio varied significantly and was anywhere from $\sim 400 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ to 800 m s^{-1} .

2.2 CHU

As originally presented by Helmboldt (2023), an observing campaign was conducted with DLITE from 2–31 Oct. 2020 using a hybrid mode with a long east/west baseline ($\sim 420 \text{ m}$) recording data at 7.85 MHz from the CHU radio station near Ottawa, Ontario and another long north/south baseline ($\sim 350 \text{ m}$) observing in the normal 35 MHz mode to monitor cosmic radio sources. Each day, data were collected from 17–22 UT when the two brightest cosmic sources, Cygnus A and Cassiopeia A were visible and while the 7.85 MHz channel was still usable. In each case, temporal SFs were calculated as described above for the two antennas receiving CHU. The phase variance between the two antennas was also calculated. While this mode did not allow for the spatial SF to be calculated, the ratio r_{coh}/t_{coh} could still be computed by determining the value of Δt at which the temporal SF was equal to this variance and taking the ratio of the baseline length to this value.

The distribution of r_{coh}/t_{coh} as a function of universal time is shown in the upper panel of Fig. 3. While there is significant spread at each time over the 30-day collection, one can see that there is a general trend of the ratio being lower at 17 UT ($\sim 150 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and higher toward the end ($\sim 250 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). As with the WWV data, the coherence time was computed using the temporal SFs, and

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Figure 2: Upper panels: Within five-minute bins, the spatial SF (dots) with temporal SFs for all antennas scaled to match (curves). In all cases, RHCP is black and LHCP is red. Lower panel: The ratio of coherence length to coherence time averaged over all four antennas. The error bars are the standard deviations among the antennas. The blue curve is a sinusoid with a period of 43 minutes fit to the data before 24 UT.

Figure 3: Upper panel: The distribution of the ratio of the coherence length to the coherence time as a function of universal time for 2–31 Oct. 2020 using the 7.85 MHz CHU skywave. The top and bottom boundaries of the shaded region are the upper and lower quartiles; the curve in between is the median. Lower panels: The (left) coherence time and (right) coherence length versus the $C_k L$ index measured at 35 MHz using cosmic radio sources.

the coherence length was estimated using this ratio. The median values of these quantities per day are plotted in the lower panels of Fig. 3 versus the daily median $C_k L$ index computed using the 35 MHz cosmic radio source data from the north/south baseline (see Helmboldt et al., 2021; Helmboldt, 2023, for more details). One can see that while there is a considerable amount of scatter within these plots, there is some indication of an anti-correlation in both cases, more so with the coherence length.

3 Discussion and Conclusions

A novel investigation of the spatial and temporal SFs for skywave propagating HF signals was conducted using an RF interferometer in southern Maryland. A single data collection of a few hours utilizing the 10 MHz skywave from WWV in Colorado in Feb. 2020 revealed coherence times on the orders of a few seconds and coherence lengths of a few hundred meters. Data obtained later that year in Oct. using the 7.85 MHz link from CHU in Ontario showed somewhat longer coherence times and lengths due to the shorter propagation distance. However, the r_{coh}/t_{coh} was similar in

both cases, being around 200 m s^{-1} .

This is much higher than the typical ion drift speeds at these latitudes, which are more typically a few to 10s of m s^{-1} . This is likely in part a projection effect as the coherence length was measured on the ground at the receive site and not within the ionosphere. At the midpoint, the ray paths that will end up at two separate antennas will be roughly twice as close together as they will be on the ground. Thus, the measured r_{coh}/t_{coh} may imply an effective irregularity velocity of $\sim 100 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. This is still somewhat higher than the expected ion drift velocity and may imply the existence of a substantial random component to the irregularities' movement. For instance, Joshi et al. (2019) found that the characteristic random velocity was often comparable to the drift velocity during scintillation events observed toward a 244 MHz geostationary beacon, albeit at a lower latitude ($\sim 22^\circ$ geographic; $\sim 13^\circ$ geomagnetic).

The assumed relationship between spatial and temporal coherence via the irregularity drift is an integral part of HF Doppler broadening calculations (Nickisch et al., 2012). Therefore, the main result of this study is both interesting and potentially important to the simulation and prediction of HF skywave channel characteristics. Of course, this is based on a relatively small amount of data. Thus, further investigation is needed to better understand the nature of the observed coherence ratios and their implication for our knowledge of skywave systems.

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